

Extreme Quantum Tunneling Image Sensing

EQuanTIS

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1. Excellence

1.1 Long-term vision

The EQuanTIS project is set to develop **entirely new image sensing method and image sensors**, collectively called quantum-tunneling imaging photodetectors (QTIP).

QTIP transduction mechanism is based on resonant quantum tunneling between cross-over points (or pixels) in cross-grid of two sets of nanowires. This new image sensing will greatly expand possibilities offered by known CCD and CMOS device.

Range of applications is extremely wide, but **we focus on satellite Earth observation**.

The advantages of QTIP are: **the ultrafast imaging** enabling real time monitoring, **high sensitivity** of the QTIP to **low-light applications** and the **large spectral wavelength range: from ultra-violet through visible to infra-red**. The smallest ever pixel size of 10X10 nm which is about 500x smaller than the smallest pixel produced today is possible in QTIP.

The devices with 256 pixels in a first phase, and 16 384 pixels in the second phase of the project will be produced and characterized. We envisage next-generation Peta-pixel QTIP image sensors for Satellite Earth observation.

Hyperspectral QTIP will expand satellite Earth observation possibilities allowing fast real-time monitoring of the food crops, vegetation, deforestation, human migrations, drought, or greenhouse gas emissions. This entirely new technology will contribute to precision farming and digitally automated agriculture, spot detection of global problem areas and other critical applications contributing to better understanding and alleviating climate, environmental and societal problems.

As reported at AZO Nanotech on Feb 28, 2023: *“Hyperspectral imaging is the ‘final frontier of earth observation’ as it reveals highly detailed and extensive insights that cannot be determined through other methods, such as conventional cameras or radars. From space, we can identify large methane emitters, measure the carbon balance in plants and soil, make global crop yield forecasts, as well as inform on issues relating to safety and security - all in real-time.”*

The EQuanTIS project brings ideas of quantum physics to create new solutions for real life problems. Quantum tunneling has only been used in a limited range of sensors, but now it is beginning to be used in Superconducting Quantum Computers - where Josephson junctions conduct pairs of electrons tunneling through a gap. *“Superconducting tunnel junction detectors (STJs) may become a viable replacement for CCDs (charge-coupled devices) for use in astronomy and astrophysics in a few years. These devices are effective across a wide spectrum from ultraviolet to infrared, and also in x-rays. The technology has been tried out on the William Herschel Telescope in the SCAM instrument.”* We must stress that QTIPs are **normal current devices** and in this alone are new and different from STJs engineering artefacts well worth studying and development.

Development of QTIPs and methods of fabrication and scaling up might very likely lead also to further development of devices which share architectural and structural likeness to QTIPs such as molecular electronic memories developed for example by J. Fraser Stoddard and James Heath group which in 2007 already reported memory devices with unprecedented density of 10^{11} bits per square centimeter. They wrote: *“Promising ingredients for advances in integrated circuit technology are nanowires, molecular electronics and defect-tolerant architectures, as demonstrated by reports of single devices and small circuits. A monolayer of bistable, [2]rotaxane molecules served as the data storage elements. Although the circuit has large numbers of defects, those defects could be readily*

identified through electronic testing and isolated using software coding.”

We stress that the above devices are all built as cross-grid nanowires configuration very similar to what we propose to develop for **light detecting devices**. Another observation is that the groups which are involved in this kind of new computer memories or new molecular computers such as Teramac prototyped by Kuekes, Heath, Stoddard, James Tour, their co-workers and students and others have also pushed boundaries of knowledge on molecular switches and electrically active, bi- and more states molecules. We stress again: in EQuanTIS project we will push this frontier of research further in the direction of identifying and testing molecules, soft matter spacers (quasi-2D molecular assemblies), perovskites and hybrid systems, e.g., solutions of nanotubes in organic liquids to explore the large parameter space of the most effective materials for light-matter interaction and light detection. To this end one of Siranga team member, Prof. Marek Samoć is the world leader in opto-sensitive 2D materials.

The consortium will be using artificial intelligence (AI) based text mining tools such as Taxila, Elicit, ChatGPT2.0 and others to conduct broad sweeps of the entire corpus of scientific literature to classify, recommend and rank various classes of candidate materials. We will be also referring to commercial market and technology intelligence material, such as *“Molecular Switches: Intellectual Property Landscape (Featuring Historical and Contemporary Patent Filing Trends, Prior Art Search Expressions, Patent Valuation Analysis, Patentability, Freedom to Operate, Pockets of Innovation, Existing White Spaces, and Claim Analysis)”* from Roots Analysis. We carefully study the market status, market trends, technology, IP landscape and competition in the Image Sensing domain. Siranga solicited comprehensive dedicated reports for CMOS, Short-Wave Infrared (SWIR) and other sensing technologies from YOLE Intelligence. We possess very detailed up-to-date proprietary information on this entire field and are aware of development directions, shortcomings of various technologies and highest opportunity directions.

The EQuanTIS project will create a proof-of-concept (PoC) device, based on resonant quantum tunneling through photo-excitabile quasi-2D materials. Quantum tunneling enables high-speed and low-energy consumption for the device and for information processing which current image sensors/camera modules on the market are not able to achieve. Using a crossbar array technology with feature sizes in the range of tens nanometers will lead to an extremely high density of the photosensitive pixels, an exceedingly high number of pixels of the order of Tera-pixels or even perhaps Peta-pixels on a large area wafers and will open up the way for different multispectral or even real time hyperspectral imagers without loss of the image resolution. PoC of our novel approach of QTIP will lead to further refinement in subsequent iterations of the photodetector that are faster and more accurate and more power efficient compared to current solutions.

Another two fascinating developments of substantial promise which might substantially benefit from processing, fabrication and device architecture developed and tested in EQuanTIS project are:

1. optical computers using memristors, which can be realised by judicious use of specific electric-field-memory molecules at cross-grid points of lattices created out of nanowires (memristors), as demonstrated by Stan Williams and collaborators, and;
2. light harvesting photovoltaic hybrid inorganic/polymer solar cells formed with laterally deposited "cross grid nanowires".

1.2 Science-towards-technology breakthrough

Our project falls into the category of “deep-tech”. It starts from an idea and a vision. The idea is well founded in the laws of quantum physics, and in some related scientific and technological precedent cases described above. However, there were never quantum tunneling based cross-grid photodetectors. The idea is unique, original (Siranga owns granted patents in seven countries) and promises *“to build on new, cutting-edge directions in science and technology to disrupt a field and a market”* and *“create new opportunities by realising innovative technological solutions”*.

Substantial enhancement of tunneling current induced by light was demonstrated for molecular bundles attached to the scanning tunneling microscope (STM) tip and shone upon by laser light. These 0-D cases will be generalised to a cross-grid of quasi-1-D nanowires separated by a quasi-2D layer of inorganic or organic soft-matter spacer(s). The very early prototypes consisting of a cross-grid of 8x8 nanowires were fabricated by NILT in Denmark and tested at labs in Singapore. However, the results were never published. Predecessor of Siranga, Quantum Precision Instruments managed between 2003 and 2007 to fabricate three generations of arrays of nanowires using different fabrication techniques, with the final samples having 12,000 nanowires of 90 nm width and 5 mm length on an area of 5 mm².

Figure 1: a) 200-mm wafer fabricated for Quantum Precision Instruments at IME Singapore (2007), b) and c) each chip had 12,000 nanowires each 90 nm wide and 5 mm long (~1/1000th width of human hair!)

The EQuanTIS project requires collaboration of scientists and engineers from several different disciplines, access to the state-of-the-art nano-fabrication facilities, and characterisation and testing instruments. It is a mix of highly imaginative and innovative science - resonant quantum tunneling through photo-excitable quasi 2-D hybrid materials, with state-of-the-art nano-fabrication techniques: nanoimprint lithography, deposition of hybrid membranes, and nanowires directly on a substrate, dip-pen lithography, spin coating, or Langmuir-Blodgett or deposition of self-assembled monolayers (SAM) and etching selected areas of membranes. There is a deep-tech mix of known, but still experimental methods with completely new techniques. Application, optimisation, and scaling of each new technique will require deep scientific understanding. Integration of various steps into one seamless and scalable production process will present very substantial scientific and technical challenges. It is expected that new scientific results, new or improved fabrication methods and new devices for entirely new applications will be obtained during the project or as a follow-up to this project.

Another objective is to choose proper materials to fabricate QTIP. Candidate materials will be researched, selected and fabrication methods suitable for their application in first laboratory samples of QTIP will be tested. The artefacts and devices will be produced and characterised both physically and functionally. Once first prototypes are fabricated process optimization and cost reductions are needed to make the process scalable.

Nanowires will be fabricated using extensive experience, technology and instruments (Nanoimprint Lithography) from Obducat. Alternative methods will be considered and tested by Fraunhofer. The novel method of creation and deposition of the second set of nanowires transferred on membrane support to form a cross-grid arrangement will be provided and mastered by Chemnitz University of Technology jointly with Fraunhofer. For the project VTT is providing MEMS Fabry-Perot Interferometers (MFPI) patented and developed by VTT. VTT will also provide characterization of tunable Fabry-Perot interferometer and will drive its system level integration with QTIP on proof-of-concept level.

Another key challenge is to overcome the chip-by-chip manufacturing by proofing of a technology concept that is applicable for scaling and volume fabrication and wafer processing in batches. Concepts of application of automated in-line test equipment, preparation of technologies to develop industry relevant technology processes to fabricate such devices after further technology adaptation and transfer to industry will be developed and tested to derive suitable approaches towards the development of commercial fabrication, speeding up commercialization in the future.

1.3 Objectives

The EQuanTIS project proof-of-concept QTIP is based on the well-established theory of quantum tunneling. Our proof-of-concept is to demonstrate in practice that theory is viable and exploitable technology can be made and further integrated into much more complex systems to enable unprecedented resolution and photo-detection.

Siranga patented technology will lead to fabrication of photodetector arrays of unprecedented qualities:

- Smallest ever pixel size of 10 nm which is about 500x smaller than the smallest pixel produced today (Omnivision 0.56 micro-m)
- The demonstration based on a relevant number of laboratory samples with a pixel number of 256 in a first phase and 16 384 pixels in the second phase of the project that will be characterised with respect to the relevant specifications.
- Largest possible number of pixels per device:
 - 10 GPixels for 1mm² sensor (for consumer devices, mobile phones, tablets)

- 1 TeraPixel for a standard 100 mm² die device (for professional photo-cameras)
- ½ PetaPixel for a full 300 mm² wafer size special photosensor (wafer-to-wafer bonded, for space and astrophysics applications)
- Relative simplicity of design – fabrication to be developed in EQuanTIS project
- Very fast image refresh time – to be measured in EQuanTIS project
- Low dark current – to be measured in EQuanTIS project
- Possibility to create “see through” fog and cloud photosensors – to be explored in EQuanTIS project

Additionally, our combined research will generate significant academic output in the form of journal articles and conference publications, proof-of-concept devices, process definitions, fabrication, and testing methods. We envisage a self-contained sub-program of research and screening of the organic dielectric monomolecular/few molecular layers materials optimally designed for the maximum photon yield - these will be very useful in their own right in photovoltaic applications.

Mass-market adoption of quantum tunneling photodetectors. Our initial products will be specialised, bespoke photosensors, designed and built for each specific application, e.g., IR, visible, UV, colour, monochrome, grayscale, as well as hyperspectral and for a specific sensor size, image data processing volume and speed. Starting with the niche space sector, moving to a larger market segment to the emerging auto industry as economies of scale allow our technology to become competitive with current market offerings. The last step is to move into the mobile telephone and consumer cameras, a truly mass-market opportunity.

Pushing the limits of integration density aiming at very high resolved crossbar arrays with the quantum photosensitive matter for tunneling current generation as active materials (spacers) between the conductors of the crossbar array is the main objective of this project. We might expect variability in individual pixel tunnel current level related to minuscule variations of inter nanowire vertical distance variations. This risk factor will be addressed by use of membranes which will remove problems related to overall wafer undulation. The other effects that will be studied and where we will be searching for viable solutions are reduction of crosstalk effects between very densely spaced pixels, the identification of reasons for pixel shortage and development of countermeasures. The homogeneity of the photosensitivity, dark current and tunneling current are further technical objectives.

In the planned follow-up R&D work outside and beyond the EQuanTIS project, we will be building devices with exceedingly large numbers of pixels, implementing signal readout demultiplexers as disclosed in the series of patents by Kuekes, Williams et al. We will be designing Digital Signal Processing (DSP) systems for signal read-out and processing using FPGAs and possibly building dedicated ASICs. Siranga has already engaged in discussions with NVIDIA to explore HPC systems enabled with GPUs to process in real-time enormous volumes of data coming from large area, very high number of pixels future quantum tunneling image sensors.

We will observe and implement the research data management best practices as required by the rules of EU and this grant regulations and created within this project. We have extensive experience in data storage, accessibility and sharing, data curation and policies.

1.4 Interdisciplinarity

The EQuanTIS project is intrinsically highly interdisciplinary, involving various fields of science and engineering such as: nanotechnology, microelectronics, theoretical physics, photo-physics and photo-chemistry, physical chemistry, organic materials, 2-D materials, photovoltaic materials, sensing, and image sensors. The project requires expertise from multiple scientific and engineering disciplines and access to experimental and fabrication facilities of the highest quality. Each of the consortium partners brings a wealth of experience, expertise, knowledge and makes their extremely specialised, highest quality experimental, production and testing facilities available to this project and all partners.

The applications of the project are diverse and wide-ranging, including aerospace, space science, satellite Earth observation, climate research, migration studies, and agriculture. Each of these areas requires specialised knowledge and skills to develop solutions that meet the specific needs of the application. The details are included in Part A of our proposal in the lists of previous involvement in R&D projects, published papers and in infrastructure that each partner will be contributing to the project.

The use of Nanoimprint Lithography, membrane science, physical chemistry, microelectronics and hyperspectral technologies further emphasises the interdisciplinary nature of the project. Each of these areas represents a unique discipline, and their integration into the project highlights the need for collaboration and expertise from multiple fields.

2. Impact

2.1 Long-term impact

Following the EIC Pathfinder Open EQuanTIS project we will focus on specific applications of tunneling Image sensors in Satellite Earth Observation aboard satellites.

High resolution radiometer on board of satellite will play a significant role in the agriculture sector for mapping soil properties, evaluating crop growth and crop loss estimates, plant health, yield and identification and quantified crop stress which could be caused by biotic and abiotic factors giving much better spatial and repeatability accuracy. It is needed for detection of crop phenology and assessment of water demand by plants in different phenological stages to provide proper irrigation management. High radiometric and spatial resolution will be needed for weed and pest detection in the early stage of different crop development. Very important is the repeatability of crop monitoring due to changes which occur during the crop growth season and needs for yield forecast. High resolution radiometer on board of satellite will provide monitoring of vegetation cover for acreage estimation, mapping and monitoring drought condition checking of nutrient and moisture status of field, weed management through precision agriculture. Monitoring of the fields will bring the reduction of ground samples and the collection of field data which is often not possible, time consuming and not spatial and time accurate, giving often, occasional UAV monitoring.

Siranga plans to address the needs of the operators of Earth observation satellites in following application areas: **weather monitoring, climate change, global soil degradation, agriculture, international security, geophysics, global navigation**, and many others.

Upon demonstration of the functioning devices, in the third year of the project, we plan to discuss specific needs with technology presidents and mission planning decision makers at European Space Agency and commercial companies such as: **SpaceX, Maxar, MDA or Planet**. Each specific mission photosensor beyond EQuanTIS project scope will be developed in very tight coordination with mission technical staff.

2.2 Innovation potential

The EQuanTIS developed QTIP with an extremely small pixel size, extremely high resolution, high sensitivity in a wide wavelength range that is suitable for spectral and hyperspectral monitoring promises a high innovation potential.

The crossbar array technology is key to multiple kinds of sensors, neuromorphic computing, in-memory computing and quantum technologies (e.g., Qubits based on colour centres). It addresses different scientific communities and different applications areas that are the focus of EQuanTIS project - however, during the course of the project the consortium members will be observing and open to channelling project discoveries and inventions to other, listed above opportunity areas.

Optical and NIR spectrum analysis and identification of chemical composition, hyperspectral imaging and identification of materials, material composition, recycling, detection of plant diseases, monitoring of status of agrarian products and food are yet another domain where EQuanTIS project might contribute new processes, materials, configurations and devices.

The fabrication process of creating two layers of extremely precisely laid out arrays of nanowires and separated with quasi-2D almost mono-molecular layer or photo-active dielectric will be a very definite nanotechnology science and engineering feat. It will most certainly advance nanolithography and pattern generation techniques.

Material sciences development of the photosensitive quantum tunneling soft matter (or other materials such as perovskites of hybrid, or special molecules solved in organic soft matter spacer) and optimization for its application in nano technology in combination with wafer processing offers yet another very promising innovation potential opportunity.

We expect a very strong synergy potential of the technology development and contribution to the scientific community.

New and different work-package components will be introduced in the follow-on activities, e.g., DSP development, signal processing system prototyping in FPGAs and real-time data streaming and analysis, large image storage and retrieval and many others.

2.3 Communication and Dissemination

The project presents very definitive opportunities for expansion of our knowledge of physical principles, materials, components, devices, performance, applications etc. All this new scientific and technological substance must and will be communicated widely in the form of conference and workshop presentations, archival open access journals, book chapters and less formal communications through blogs and community discussions as well as partner’s own web portals and, where appropriate, general press announcements. The detailed “Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication activities” will be developed within 6 months of the project start.

We do have very substantial experience in scientific publishing, and especially in Open Access publishing and this will be one of the main channels of communication and dissemination of the new knowledge. We will identify the most suitable, highest ranking archival open access journals and the leading technical conferences and we will strive to submit our material there and to get accepted.

3. Quality and efficiency of the implementation

3.1 Work plan and allocation of resources

Below we present a coarse-grained PERT chart of the Work packages dependencies.

The Gantt Chart is presented in the following page. The project management tools we use, including Gantt Chart editor, resources inventory, timeline, dependencies between Work Packages and individual tasks are planned in a very detailed way. The wealth and granularity of project management insight is not

3.2 Siranga

Siranga team members bring the following strengths and expertise to the project:

Dr Marek T. Michalewicz, Founder and CEO

- 40 years of experience in Physics, Computational Science, Research Management; and computational infrastructure management in Australia, USA, Singapore and Poland
- inventor of IP portfolio of a family of seven patents granted in the USA, China, Japan, UK, Germany, France and Singapore describing the quantum tunneling photodetector device based on cross-grid of nanowires.
- supervised design of early rudimentary prototype of the photodetector fabricated by NILT in Denmark and consisting of 8x8 nanowires on glass substrate. Supervised early tests at National Measurement Laboratories in Singapore.
- expertise in project and organisation management: MTM was a director of Supercomputing Centres in Singapore and Poland (last 13 years) and has 23+ years of experience as a CEO, CTO and Founder of five start-ups.
- Open Science expertise: Dr M. Michalewicz was the Polish representative of “Read & Publish Study”, “Big Deals” and “Chief Negotiators Group” of the European University Association (2019-2021). He was a member of European Open Scientific Cloud Task Force - EOSC TF on Technical Interoperability of Data and Services (2021). As a Director of Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling (ICM), University of Warsaw Dr Michalewicz was responsible for Virtual Library of Science which provided access to 26,000 journal titles and 157,000 books to about 500 academic and R&D institutions in Poland hosted on ICM as well as publishers’ resources. He helped to negotiate almost 4000 pre-paid open access publications annually for Polish authors with all scientific publishers, including 1000 with Elsevier and 2,100 with Springer. ICM created Open Library of polish scientific publications with over 500,000 articles, 1,628 journals and 1,345 books.
- Interdisciplinary Research expertise: Dr Michalewicz worked at two major multidisciplinary national research organisations: Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO) in Australia (1990-2000) as a Principal Research Scientist and at Agency for Science, Technology and Research (A*STAR) in Singapore (2009-2016) as the CEO of A*STAR Computational Resource Centre - serving close to 5,500 strong research

organisation. Between 2018-2021 Dr Michalewicz was a Director of Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling, University of Warsaw.

Prof. NN He has been involved in research of novel radiation detectors based on nanomaterials since 1995. He and his teams published several papers and obtained two international patents in this area. This research was performed in laboratories in Australia, Germany, Poland, Singapore and USA. He was a group leader in GSI, Darmstadt, Germany (2000-2003) where he developed radiation detector based on boron-doped CVD diamond. For this work his group obtained a patent. The licence for this patent was purchased by SIEMENS. Between 2004-2007 he was a beamline scientist at Singapore Synchrotron Light Source where he was responsible for development of the imaging beamline and radiation detector based on 1D nanomaterials for which he received patent in USA. He spent one year at ANKA synchrotron in Karlsruhe, Germany where he was an imaging beamline group leader. Between 2008-2011 he was employed at Monash University, Melbourne, Australia as a senior beamline scientists at the Australian Synchrotron.

Since 2011 he is a group leader at the University of Rzeszow in Rzeszow, Poland involved with development of new imaging techniques for biology and medicine. For almost 30 years he has been involved in research in material science and development and applications of radiation detectors and novel materials and nanomaterials. Prof. Cholewa gained experience in leading research laboratories around the world. Between 1998-2006 he was a leader of a commercial company, MC Scientific Consulting involved in scientific and commercial instruments and project design and management. His scientific leadership and commercial expertise and experience will be critical in managing work of the Consortium members.

Prof. NN, Scientific Advisor, Materials Science, 2D dielectric materials

- expert in physics and chemistry of advanced materials, with particular experience in light-matter interactions. He graduated in Poland but worked in Australia (17 years at the Laser Physics Centre, ANU, Canberra), USA and Canada before returning to Poland in 2008 and establishing a high profile research group focusing on nanobiophotonics at Wroclaw University of Science and Technology.

- through the appointment at the University (currently holding a prestigious position of Professor Magnus) the possibility of facilitating specialist commissioned work in the University laboratories (e.g. advanced nanoscale imaging)

- author of over 400 publications, Hirsch index = 62 (Scopus); major achievements concerning nonlinear optical properties of organometallics, nanomaterials and metal-organic frameworks.

- member of the National Research Centre (Poland) Council for term 2018-2022, supervising grant application handling procedures for chemistry. During that term transition to fully international expert panels has been achieved. Participation in the Appeal Committee for two years has broadened for Prof. Samoć the perspective of assessments of grants and their results, including publishing models.

Professor NN, Scientific Advisor, Satellite Earth observation, its Requirements and Applications

Her main research interests are related to the use of information derived from optical and microwave sensors for water and energy balance for various soil-vegetation cover. Development of the methodology of heat transfer between the vegetation layer and the air applying information from remote sensing. She is developing models for crop yield forecasting, crop growth assessment, environmental monitoring, drought detection and monitoring, detection of water deficit and its impact on yield reduction, natural hazards and wetlands management. Modelling CO₂ sequestration applying satellite data. Participant in international projects: FP6 Geoland, FP7 Geoland2, ESA *Express Procurement Sentinel-1 Soil Moisture Product Validation*. She is the principal investigator of Polish-Norwegian Research Projects: FINEGRASS, Grassat.

Tables for section 3.1

Table 3.1a: List of work packages (WP)

WP No	Work package Title	Start Month	End month
1	Project Management	1	36
2	Definition of the product and processes	1	6
3	Study and selection of the optimal candidate for the dielectric soft matter spacer	1	30
4	Fabrication feasibility study - fabbing small batch of laboratory sample devices including application of soft matter spacer	7	30
5	Physical characterisation of the devices	8	36
6	Fabrication of FPI and system level integration with QTIP	3	36
7	Functional characterisation of the devices	8	36

Table 3.1b: Work package description

Work package number	1
Work package title	Project Management, Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

Objectives:

- Overseeing the entire project performance and seamless flow, coordination of efforts between partners and enabling continuous communication and cooperation between the parties and adherence to project goals and EIC Pathfinder grant rules and regulations and EU regulations.
- Protect IP and develop an exploitation plan outlining a strategy for commercialization
- Dissemination of results
- Data Management
- All partners contribute to these objectives, are involved in all tasks Siranga leads this WP.

Description of work: The aim of this WP is to manage the entire project at the highest level, to coordinate activities of all five project consortium partners and performance of the tasks described below.

The tasks are self-evident and will not be further elaborated.

Lead partner:

Task 1.1 Project Management and coordination of tasks among the members of consortium.

Task 1.2 Quality Assurance and Risk Management

Task 1.3 Management of funds

Task 1.4 Technical Management

Task 1.5 Planning, arrangement and leadership in regular bi-weekly project progress tele-conferences

Task 1.6 Planning and implementation of open science practices and publications

Task 1.7 Project data and records management according to FAIR principles and development of a detailed DMP

Task 1.8 Responsibility for IP strategy and delivery of IP agreements between consortium members

Task 1.9 Responsibility for developing, managing and execution of a detailed Communication and Dissemination Plan

Task 1.10 Preparation of continuity plan and activities leading to securing continuation of R&D work beyond 36 months for specific target application

Work package number	2
Work package title	Definition of the QTIP laboratory sample

Objectives: This basic and important WP focuses on joint discussions among all partners leading to elucidation of the physical dimension of the device/chip, including placement and type of terminal points or contacts. Discussions and decisions on material selection for the nanowires (opposing layers of nanowires do not have to be made of the same material), selection of dielectric quasi-2D layers, also taking into consideration ease of laboratory handling and design of testing stages. Overall, main objective is to come to a consensus on the physical specifications of the device to ensure successful processing and eventually a functional device.

Description of work

Task 2.1 Device design: Physical dimensions of the device and the chip. Determination of contacts and their placement on the chip.

Task 2.2 Materials design: Discussion and Selection of the materials for the nanowires and quasi-2D layer. This task is in interaction with WP3.

Task 2.3 Fabrication requirements: optimisation of the device design for device performance and manufacturability.

Task 2.4 Manufacturing process: Development of individual process steps to meet device specifications and integration of manufacturing process steps to device process flow.

Task 2.5 Specifications for the device testing: General specification for device testing processes and stages for physical characterisation. Actual device testing is performed in WP7.

Work package number	3
Work package title	Study and selection of the optimal candidate for the dielectric soft matter spacer

Objectives: Main objective of this work package is to find the best material for the soft matter dielectric/photoconductor which will be used in the initial tests and later in the demonstrator devices. It includes the assessment regarding performance of the target function of the photo effect (e.g. sensitivity, time behaviour, low nonlinearity, voids), coating (e.g. homogeneity, adhesion strength) and robustness in further fabrication process steps (evaporation and structuring of a top metal layer for example).

Description of work

Lead partner:

Task 3.1 Literature Survey: Literature survey to find out potential candidates for the photoresponsive dielectric spacer, with the following characteristics:

- low dark conductivity
- fast and efficient photogeneration of excited species mediating the enhancement of the tunneling current
- robustness under various types of external conditions and under electromagnetic irradiation in the required wavelength region
- immediate or almost immediate availability (the synthesis of the material must be well developed)
- processability in the form of very thin films using the chosen deposition technique.

This task will be accomplished using Taxila AI global scientific literature and text mining software combined with dedicated scripts using awk, grep, Julia and involving also Elicit and other modern tools.

Task 3.2 Physical and Physicochemical Testing of the Short-Listed Candidates

Task 3.3 Testing of the Deposition Techniques Using Standard Substrates

Task 3.4 Micro- and Nanofabrication Steps for Photo Responsive Dielectric Materials: Treatment of samples with photo responsive dielectric material by relevant micro and nano fabrication technology steps

- deposition and structuring of metals including deposition of photoresist and etching of the metal

- deposition of dielectric materials including deposition of photoresist and etching of the metal
Annealing at different temperatures in different atmosphere

Work package number	4
Work package title	Fabrication feasibility study - fabrication of small batches of laboratory sample devices including application of soft matter spacer

Objectives Laboratory samples of a first fully functional device type with reduced complexity (first technology run) and of a second type with high complexity after iterative re-design (second technology run)

Description of work (where appropriate, broken down into tasks), lead partner and role of participants.
Deliverables linked to each WP are listed in table 3.2c (no need to repeat the information here).

Lead partner:

Task 4.1 Investigation of soft matter integration schemes and layer stack optimization. Identify pros and cons of single wafer technology versus integration of soft matter material by wafer bonding

Task 4.2 Technology pre-runs for nanowire patterning by e-beam-lithography. Optimization of process parameters. Wafer processing for first fabrication run including inline measurement during the wafer fabrication and integration during the first fabrication run targeting fully functional samples.* The results are evaluated by WP5

Task 4.3 Development of a technology sequence for fabrication of fully functional devices. Integration of soft matter and layer stack. Wafer processing for a second fabrication run including inline measurement during the wafer fabrication and integration during the first fabrication run targeting fully functional samples.* The results are evaluated by WP 5.

Task 4.4 Resume and derivation of fabrication sequence for a higher number of samples as an optimized version. Patterning by nano imprint lithography.

* The fabrication runs will be based on a fine pitch crossbar array technology using nano imprint lithography of a thin film metal layer that is embedded into an isolation material. The metal surface will be made freely accessible by damascene technology. The technology parameters need to be developed since the materials composition and the adhesion strength of the metal and isolating material on one hand side to the soft matter on the other hand side is not yet characterized. Process adaptation including activation procedures, pre-treatment processes and a variation of materials are expected to be applied. The dimensions of the crossbar structure exclude wet chemical processes such as lift-off or wet etching to generate the pattern structure of the metals and dielectric, respectively. Therefore, the metal layers of the crossbar structures will be fabricated by damascene-like process flows. In order to prevent or reduce parasitic capacities over the intra and inter layer dielectrics an insulating material with a very low dielectric constant (k- value) is needed. The defined targeted structural dimensions (CD < 100 nm) require the use of e-beam lithography and nanoimprint processes. The layouts for the necessary layers are defined in WP2. Lithographic processes are being developed which allow the very small structures of the upper and lower layer as well as the associated connection pads to be realised in a single plane. For this purpose, inter and intra level lithographic mix and match approaches have to be used to increase the throughput of e-beam lithography (focused on smaller structures) as the exposure since larger structures can be exposed with i-line stepper lithography (CD > 350 nm). This is applied and further developed, to fabricate at least 4 master tamps (bottom metal lines, soft matter spacer dots, top metal lines) in different layout variations due to possible exposure time. Depending on the integration scheme developed in WP2, the soft matter mask will be designed as both a positive mask and a negative mask. Thus, we will be able to investigate a gap fill processes and direct patterning processes of the soft matter spacer in parallel.

For the second metal layer highly selective non-continues reactive ion etching processes will be performed to etch the intra layer dielectric and the top metal layer of the crossbar structure. Both processes will be investigated to achieve no degradation of the underneath soft matter spacer. In this context, post etch treatments sequences will be also investigated in order to remove etch resist with low damage impact to the soft matter spacer material.

Work package number	5
Work package title	Physical characterisation of the devices and of fabrication test samples

Objectives:

- Material specifications (dielectric soft matter) regarding the functional properties and robustness in the fabrication technology as a base point for the definition of the material composition and fabrication technology sequence.
- Characteristics of the research samples at every stage of the fabrication process line

Description of work:

Task 5.1: Characterization of the electric, optical and mechanical parameters of the soft matter samples from WP3 and after integration in WP 4 (flatness, roughness, hardness, dielectric spacer thickness, contact angle, adhesion strength, refractive index, chemical composition with FTIR/ATR, CPS, Auger spectrometry, variable spectral ellipsometry, nano indentation, atomic force microscopy, pull test, FIB/SEM)

Task 5.2: Characterization of the detector samples regarding the specified parameters e. g. nanowire conductivity, current/voltage characteristic, the cross talk between lines and between pixels and the degradation of isolation properties.

Task 5.3: A radiation hardness test will be conducted using a Co60 source aiming at observation of the influence of ionising radiation to the degradation of the soft matter and the functional characteristic.

Work package number	6
Work package title	Fabrication and integration of MFPI

Objectives

Work package 6 is concentrated on design and optimization of the optical filter and finally manufacturing of the tunable optical filter from visible (VIS) to SWIR (shortwave infrared) with a narrow bandwidth. Eventually the purpose is to make a proof-of-concept (PoC) spectrometer with system level integration of the optical filter with QTIP fabricated in WP6 and WP4, respectively.

Description of work

Task 6.1 Filter Design and Optimization: Design and optimization of tunable optical filter to meet the wavelength specifications required for sensing applications from VIS to SWIR.

Task 6.2 Fabrication of the optical filter: Fabrication of the tunable optical filter to meet the set specifications. Optimization of the manufacturing process to ensure reproducibility and scalability.

Task 6.3 System level integration: System level integration of the proof-of-concept QTIP and integration of optical filters with the detector arrays to realise a PoC spectrometer. Besides system level integration, this includes electrical and optical designing and building of the electro-optical system and signal interfacing.

Work package number	7
Work package title	Functional characterisation of the devices

Objectives

Work package 7 focuses on thorough functional characterization of the fabricated devices. To benchmark the devices, their measured characteristics will be compared with the state-of-the-art devices. Here electro-optical characterization of fabricated devices is performed. And measured characteristics and characterised performance are compared to the state-of-the-art (SoA) imaging photodetectors and application targets.

Description of work

Task 7.1 Building of the Characterization Setup: Design and building of the characterisation stages, optical tables as well as designing characterization processes to ensure that the testing is performed accurately.

Task 7.2 Electro-Optical Characterization and Performance Evaluation: The experimental design for the electro-optical characterization is developed, and the necessary setups are prepared and tested for the devices used in this study. The devices are characterised by measuring noise and dark current characteristics of the photodetectors, responsivity, quantum efficiency, response time, and spectral response. Furthermore, relevant figures-of-merits such as noise-equivalent power (NEP) and specific detectivity D^* will be obtained and compared with the state-of-the-art imaging photodetectors. The performance will be evaluated against the specific targets for the sensing application of the project.

Task 7.3 Testing and Optical/Functional Characterisation: Fabricated components are characterised for dark current, quantum efficiency, responsivity, spectral response, range, noise characteristics, response time/refresh rate for example.

Table 3.1c: List of Deliverables

No	Deliverable name	Short description	WP No	Type	Delivery date (in months)
D1.1	Dissemination, exploitation & communication plan	Plan with expected dissemination actions and the updated result (interim and final reports)	1	Report	M06, M36
D1.2	Data Management Plan	Plan for Data Management (interim and final)	1	Report	M06, M36
D1.3	Progress Reports for EC	EC progress reports (interims and final)	1	Report	M12, M24, M36
D6.1	Optical filter test report	Characterization results of the optical filter fabricated by VTT.	6	Report	M18
D7.1	Electro-optical characteristics and performance evaluation of devices	Report of measured electro-optical characteristics and performance evaluation of photodetectors	7	Report	M30
3	Soft matter samples	Samples with soft matter on substrate	3	Sample	M18
4	Function samples I	Fully functional samples with low complexity	4	Sample, Report	M23
5	Function samples II	Fully functional samples with high complexity	4	Sample, Report	M29
6	Physical test results	Results of physical tests of the samples I and samples II	5	Report	M34

Table 3.1d: List of milestones

Milestone number	Milestone name	Related work package (s)	Due date (in month)	Means of verification
MS1	Device and material specifications for the QTIP	WP2 WP3	M6	Physical specifications and material specifications are set for the QTIP.
MS2	Design and process integration for the QTIP	WP2 WP3 WP4	M8	Device design is finalised. Separate process steps are tested for new materials and integrated into a process flow.
MS3	Finished QTIP device run	WP4	M12	Full process run for QTIP
MS4	Functional optical filter (FPI)	WP6	M12	Optical filters characterised to meet the device specifications.
MS5	Electro-optical measurements of first QTIP devices	WP7	24	Successful device characterization to meet the specs
MS6	Functional samples I	WP 4	23	Functional samples I are ready for test
MS7	Functional Sample II	WP 4	29	Functional samples II are ready for test
MS8	System level integration of fabricated devices	WP6	30	Fabricated and characterised components are integrated at a system level to demonstrate the functionality of the concept.

Table 3.1e: Critical risks for implementation

Description of risk (indicate level of (i) likelihood, and (ii) severity: Low/Medium/High)	WP(s) involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
PoC detector fabrication is late [i: H; ii: H]	WP4	
PoC detector is not functional or does not meet the specs [i: M, ii: H]	WP4	Process iteration is done to fabricate functional components and to overcome materials or process integration issues.
Optical filters are late due to processing issues or do not meet the specs [i: L; ii: M]	WP6	Process iteration is done if needed after the first device fabrication round.
System level integration is not possible due to lack of functional off-the-shelf components [i: M; ii: H]	WP6	There is no substitute for a PoC detector and if the detector is not ready or does not meet the specs, system level integration cannot be done. Optical filter can be replaced with a new fabrication round.
Dielectric soft matter undergoes a too strong degradation by the further fabrication processes [i: M; ii: M]	WP3, WP4, WP5, WP7	Pre-tests in WP4, Task 4.2 Iterative interaction of Task 4.2 and WP3
Short cuts at cross points reduce the number of functional lines and rows [i: M; ii: M]	WP3, WP4, WP5	Investigation of the reason of short cuts Changes in the material choice

Ethics Issues: The use of AI

Ethical risks of the use of AI in the project are related to the availability of the corpus of scientific literature and the methods of reviewing and analysing articles performed by algorithms. The results will indirectly affect the

decision-making processes in the project - they will be the basis for further research in this field, and thus also a contribution to its development. In practice, they will support the decision-making process on the selection of a specific material.

The indicated risks will be limited by a critical analysis performed by the developer at every stage of obtaining results from the algorithms. The developer as a team member is well aware that she will use AI-supported tools and has the knowledge and skills to evaluate them. It is also possible to have limited insight into the algorithms and to modify them directly in the AI toolchain itself. In addition, the results from AI-supported searches will only support research, while their final shape will be decided by world-class experts who are members of the team. They will also make a substantive assessment of the results obtained from AI tools. Another preventive measure taken to avoid bias will be to provide the widest and most diverse corpus of key-reviewed literature that has been peer-reviewed by reviewers even before entering the AI system. Also, we can consider a rigorous approval process for new materials as a preventive measure - each search result will be verified for toxicity and safety measures before being used in laboratory procedures.

The team's thorough risk assessment and proposed countermeasures will be valid throughout the project's life cycle and will ensure a high ethical level of research, with respect for fundamental human rights and freedoms.